
NEED FOR NEW BRANCH “INTRICACY PSYCHOLOGY” AND INTRICATE CASE HISTORY TAKING FOR NEW INTERVENTION MEDITATION

Prof. G. S. Ramesh Kumar

Consulting Psychologist, Wonderfeelz, Neuropsy Meditation Studio, Coimbatore, India

E-mail address: consultingpsychologist@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In this paper current author proposes a need for studying intricate differences between psychological aspects, factors, cognitions, affect, behaviour and related dynamics. It can be promoted as a separate branch within the domain of Psychology as Intricacy Psychology. Case history taking for the new Intervention Meditation of current author is proposed in line with capturing such intricacies of the client. The current also proposes to study the intricacies belonging to ‘Self’ as an important factor within his new Intervention Meditation approach. View of Self in line with current author’s new Intervention Meditation is also outlined. This paper is at the initial stage of the series of papers planned to develop his new Intervention Meditation approach which is entirely different from all other meditations in vogue.

Keywords: *Intervention Meditation, Hierarchy of Progressive Stages, Psychology of Intricacies, Intricate Case History taking*

1. INTRICACIES

There is a need to elaborate on explicit principles, concepts and notions of psychology that exist so far and would be discovered in future too. For centuries, psychologists ended up in focusing on conclusions and hypotheses in attempt to elaboration. Current author suggests that such an elaboration can take another new dimension of “intricacies” or “studying intricate differences between psychological factors and dynamics”. Discussion of Hedge, Craig., Powell, Georgina & Sumner, Petroc (2017) in detail outline variability and inherent flaws along with the causes. Such instances miss to address delicate differences. Hence a new mission, to address such intricacies which are traditionally missed out, is warranted.

Intricacies can be seen *between the notions*. For example, explicit access to innate ideas (such as substance, duration, etc. mean Self-Reflection by Descartes, and to Locke, self-reflection is simply a part of experience (Azeri, Siyaves 2011). Psychologists all along continued to take a side or produce a new side / notion/ conclusion / hypothesis. But most ignored precious things are that the intricate differences between such closely overlapping notions do exist but suppressed by arrived conclusions. Those ‘*intricate differences*’ which remain as Ground (as in terms of Gestalt) never brought to foreground as ‘figure’. In other words, why such intricacies exist, what are contributions of such intricacies on understanding the concepts, what directions such intricacies give to logics preferred and conclusions drawn subsequently, what directions do such intricacies impose upon cognitive functions in broad terms and external manifestations (behaviour), how such resultant broad spectrum cognitive functions and external manifestations do interplay with producing further intricacies (deepening) are conveniently forgotten areas.

Current author likes to propose this gap be pushed to the forefront and a separate branch to address these be initiated.

While the basic or pure *branch of intricacies* (branch within Psychology) could deal with the subject matter of “*studying intricate differences between overlapping concepts, what psychosocial conditions and knowledge levels lead to production of such intricacies, individual differences in orientation (including traits) to producing such intricacies, and what are contributions of such intricacies on understanding the concepts, what directions such intricacies give to logics preferred and conclusions drawn subsequently*”.

On the other hand, *applied branch* of the intricacies deals with “*what directions do such intricacies impose upon cognitive functions in broad terms and external manifestations (behaviour), how such resultant broad spectrum cognitive functions and external manifestations do interplay with producing further intricacies (deepening) are conveniently forgotten areas*”.

This new branch would have a pervasive influence on every field where human idea involved such as psychotherapy, and discoveries / inventions / innovations in medical sciences research, pharmaceutical sciences, engineering etc.

Some examples could help understand better. In one Personal instance, Mr. A says, 'I will come tomorrow' to Mr. B. Mr. B gets a thought with intricate difference assuming 'Mr. A will come but may be a few minutes late'.

In the above example, both share a common notion that Mr. A will turn up next day and meet Mr. B.

An attitude questionnaire item will also bring out the same score (therefore objective) of Mr. B toward Mr. A to a probable question "Do you think Mr. A keeps up his words?".

Now it is clear that such psychometric tools can measure only compromised responses and not intricacies or intricate differences. Such psychometric tools may be addressing wider differences by way of factor analysis and other cluster analysis methods, but not intricate differences as just explained.

The missing precious points could be, what is the intricate difference between the notion Mr A assumes about Mr.B that he is assured of his turning up the next day and Mr. B's notion that 'may be a few minutes late'.

Applying the subject matter of Basic / Pure branch of Intricacy Psychology as outlined above, the cognitions of Mr. B are influenced not only by the fact that Mr. A will turn up but the intricacies that:

What is the difference between Mr. B thinking about Mr. A "he will turn up" and "he will turn up but late"? (Studying intricate differences between overlapping aspects)

What traits, motivation, attitude, needs, or external situations / clues produced the intricate difference in the impression in Mr. B as intended by Mr. A and what actual impression was experienced in the mind of Mr. B for the same effort of Mr. A (what psychosocial conditions and knowledge levels lead to production of such intricacies, individual differences in orientation (including traits) to producing such intricacies)

What influence is made in the mind of Mr. B not by the overt understanding "Mr. A will turn up late a few minutes" but by the intricate difference between the impression intended by Mr. A and actual impression experienced by Mr. B (what are contributions of such intricacies on understanding the concepts)

Even in a counselling interaction these sentences and differences may happened to be highlighted by the counselling psychologist, but imperceptibly slipping into a 'conclusion' or another idea. While the intricacy psychology needs to study deeper into the dynamics that produced the intricacies.

What kind of directions such intricate difference takes – whether influences logic, motivation, perception, attitude, affect etc. This is a tricky juncture. While such a difference can influence all these directions but not uniformly. Consider, Mr. B agrees with the situation or even habit of Mr. A but his motivation for cooperation be coloured by cautiousness. Alternatively, Mr. B cooperates with Mr. A but likes to change his attitude toward Mr. A for future interactions.

In taking the point just above, in Mr. B agreeing with the situation or habit but not his motivation to

cooperate what logics are preferred by Mr. B and what conclusions drawn or new schema formed by Mr. B? (What directions such intricacies give to logics preferred and conclusions drawn subsequently)

Such an analysis is evident in psychometric tool's statements too – what the statement implies what the impression created in the mind of respondent (not the forced choice answer).

Taking the Applied aspects, What Cognitive processes occur in response to such intricacies in Mr. B

(What directions do such intricacies impose upon cognitive functions in broad terms as a result of conclusions or new schema formed in Mr. B.)

These are again intricately different to his overt conclusion of any how I will cooperate or any how I will change my attitude toward Mr. A.

What changes occur in the external manifestations (behaviour), how such resultant broad spectrum

cognitive functions and external manifestations do interplay with producing further intricacies (deepening) are conveniently forgotten areas.

Here, too an intricacy is hidden. Some may see the phrase “external manifestation” and ‘behaviour’ as one and same, while, some see intricate difference – behaviour as demonstrable / replicable and “external manifestation” as inclusive of the indemonstrable or unexplainable ‘impression’ too.

Thus, human interactions are full of intricacies / intricate differences other than demonstrated or overt differences.

As these intricacies are not the domain of physiotherapy (physical movements/ therapy healing muscles, nerves and bones) nor the Occupational Therapy (activities of daily living and modifications) nor any other field, but at the core of Psychology (cognition, emotion, behaviour processes).

Importantly, such intricacies cannot be dealt by non-psychologists as it involves deeper analysis at the core further to existing psychological analyses and processes (both conscious and unconscious). Such an analysis of intricacies will require thorough knowledge in every branch of psychology such as personality psychology, abnormal & clinical, organizational, consumer, community & social psychologies.

Research data are not immune to such intricacies have. Differences between self-reports and peer-reports were well demonstrated (Butkovic A, and Modrusan I., 2021). Assuming similarities in experience and undermining delicate differences in emotional experiences, leads to biases (Jolly and Chang, 2019).

In research too, the newly proposed branch will have its own directions to progress. For example, consider research finding related to individual differences in crystal intelligence. While the pattern of individual differences indicated that crystalized intelligence influences metaphor comprehension across a broad range of metaphor types, whereas individual differences in fluid intelligence mainly impact comprehension of more cognitively complex metaphors, such as those that arise in literary sources (Stamenković, D., & Holyoak, K. J. 2018). The usual way forward for this would be understanding relationship among analogical reasoning, creative metaphors, reasoning processes that operate at the level of lexical semantics etc.

But the branch newly proposed by current author would see the dynamics involved at deeper level at an intricate difference where the crystal intelligence and fluid intelligence share a commonality and just start differing at the minute strength (could the new branch be called Source Psychology, as dealing with ‘sources’ of minute differences between two psychological aspects?). See diagram 1 that only ‘represents’ the idea of intricate differences.

1.1 Intricate Case History Taking

Case history taking is important step in the new Intervention Meditation approach of current author, that has been dealt in different source. Case history for the current author's Intervention Meditation approach should essentially be the tool of psychology of intricacies. In other words, the case history taking according to current author's Intervention Meditation approach should delve into the intricacies belonging to the client.

The case history taking for the meditation technique according to current author should be in two stages - one outline case study in traditional psychiatric case history format. The second stage should be on the individual's perceived problems in domains of Quality of Life. The purpose of this is to analyze the Stages / hierarchies he formed in the past for his goals in various domains. The current author's (Ramesh Kumar G S 1999) view that everything can be arranged in a hierarchy of progressive stages got endorsement through rather a separate and unrelated work of Friston and Stephen (2007), that the world is modelled as a hierarchy by brain.

Current author had mentioned that hierarchy of progressive stages are made possible only by forming continuum of the psychological factor/ situation taken for work up. In such a hierarchy formation and passing through stages, the 'essences' are filtered into the mind of the individual and his psyche is elaborating by coalescence of such essences. While the response system within the individual forms required continua by itself, individuals need to make voluntarily for external objects. For example, one arranges a continuum of engine performance as essence and arranges brands of cars from one end to other. Hierarchy is inherent in any continuum and stages are automatic. As much as one gain required information for each stage, his mind passes through progressive stages smoothly and perception of progress results. Depending on information, level of mastery and smoothness of progressing through stages and one may feel Perception of Progress get associated with any model from lower end to higher end (that is why all brands are sold and each brand has its own 'segment of people' based on Perception of Progress). In other words, one may have a liking with Brand A but may feel Perception of Progress with Brand J.

In case history taking for Intervention Meditation approach of current author, expert / Guru should check the pattern of hierarchy of progressive stages formed by his client and the proper and improper stages having been formed by the client. The expert / Guru should also, very importantly, check for the client's realization / feel Vs Observation / Verification / Comparison efforts – as, while the former enhances smooth passing through hierarchy of progressive stages and perception of progress, the latter entails stagnation / obsession.

Case history taking is a more reflective stage in which the Psychologist understands the pattern usually adopted by the client and formulate specific assessment required. Current author adopts unique approach of his meditation approach with pre-set measurable goals, unlike in other meditations. This is because of the very nature of goal itself. For a better understanding, the expert should get information about the client's information for two valid reasons: one the expert should get information about the general characteristics, coping, life style, attitudes, and parenting belonging to client's parents. This serves the purpose of contrasting the psychosocial background in which the client grew. Second valid reason for such an elaboration of parental atmosphere by client also helps the psychologist to understand the persistent views of client towards his or her parental atmosphere.

The case history should yield an in-depth qualitative baseline to begin the current author's Intervention Meditation approach. Clinical interventions should account for baseline characteristics to ensure that participants are referred to the most effective, suitable programs for their own needs (Antoine et al 2018). Clients also should get certain benefit from proper and elaborate case history taking process. The client should get a convincing message that the hierarchy of progressive stages formation is crucial and how he / she passed through such stages formation in the past.

The detailed case history taking should also focus on the readiness of the client for change and undergo meditative sessions. This view already shared by others that screening the nonmotivated Clients, low motivation itself set as starting point and brief motivational enhancement interventions initiated before starting actual therapy (Ryan, R M 2011). Both psychologist and client should realize that even the inner experience and Core Feel has continuum and therefore hierarchical stages of progress. All that part of the grand life's hierarchy of progressive stages. The Intricate Case History taking gives two sets of baseline data which enhances quality of the work (see diagram 2 above).

The case history taking is followed by the preparation including Sankalp (the stage of resolution to attain preselected goal), and initiating meditative behaviour procedurally according to the needs, situations, traits, psychosocial background and goals selected.

Preparing Response System:

As one is relaxed more, his internal response system aligns automatically with his self and immediate environment. It is not his voluntary efforts to align but happens automatically.

This is crucial for his "clue recognition", Insight and intuition. For enhanced mental energy required for insight / intuition building process at Core Feel, energy guessing technique is used. This is not to be used in isolation like a quack. This strong warning is needed in the interest of client's well-being and ethical professional practice. The qualified psychologist who is trained to become Expert / Guru, should be trained to use this method properly as an embedded one in the preparation stage of meditation. Accordingly, after each part's sensation, the Subject should feel the Energy in mind and identify it as positive or negative, feel the dimensions - direction, movement, stagnation, polarity as in dilemma etc. of the energy. Though it is explained in couple sentences it involves skill and depth of psychological. Knowledge vehemently

As one indulges in meditative behaviour he comes across discrete instances of his Core Feel crops up readily. This is to be identified by the Expert / Guru, after thorough verification by analyzing introspective response of the client.

This "automatic crop up" of Core Feel readily is PRIMARY Meditative benefit; produced by neuropsychological response system of the individual. The SECONDARY one is resulting by the meditative behaviour. The smooth passing of stages in the tasks / steps to goal in non-meditative situations but identified by Expert / Guru and the client as well, are the PROCESS (Progressive Process or Progressive Stages) benefits.

Core Feel elaborates to form complexity of 'Self', while Self is comprised of two dimensions – Identity and Self-Direction (Lorenzini, N., et.al 2021). The Self automatically aligns with immediate environment in such a way that any involuntary or habitual attention immediately stimulates an affect (not Core Affect) of the object's relation to one's self and smoothly (i.e., without need for further voluntary control efforts) returns to previous internal / external stimulus. Thus, this ability makes an important dimension of healthy mind. The method to study Self, needs revisiting.

Awareness of quantitative modeling based on self-report data and analyzing verbal narratives can alert other researchers to the issues of multiple selves and the role of unconscious generalizations in how people feel, think, and behave in different situations (Horowitz, M J.,2012). In case history taking process also, 'self' is given much importance unlike in traditional case history taking. This is because of the fact that 'self' is most influenced by individual differences. "Self" also characterized collectively but differentially in different conditions such as paranoid, anger and anxiety states as mentioned earlier (Nobre, Pedro J. and Pinto-Gouveia, José 2009).

While ego depletion is linked to mistaken understanding of self-control, the existence of ego-depletion itself is dubious and misguided (Baumeister, R F., Tice, D M., and Vohs, K D 2018). This nature of continuously revised understanding of the bond between Self, Ego and Energy is also one reason why the case history for the meditation approach by current author, should be prepared only by a qualified psychologist of core and experienced.

Self-observing capacities as discussed by Tanzilli, A et.al (2021) is necessary to be understood and a specific mentioning be made in the case history of the client. There should be a balance between such focused attention and unfocused attention. In unfocused attention stimuli available to all sensory organs are inclusively processed. The intricate case history taking for new intervention meditation of current author should tap these aspects.

In case the involuntary / habitual attention object persists, it is brought on a continuum with the previous internal / external stimulus, forming a smooth hierarchy of progressive stages resulting in a smooth affect due to perception of progress. A real change or improvement is multifaceted if initiated by natural response system of the individual. There should be a simultaneous alteration in character, attitude, coping style and arousal level than these were so far. New Intervention Meditation of the current author should be given by only qualified and well-trained Psychologist because it involves self-conscious process and self-conscious process induces anxiety and self-doubt. The Expert / Guru should lead the meditative intervention in such a tricky way that self-conscious process occurs but without inducing anxiety or self-doubt.

The Expert / Guru doesn't use pre-selected principles or use predetermined "modules" for such things are unrealistic and only an attempt to impose limitations of the therapist onto the client. Instead, the psychologist applies relevant psychological principles to understand every successive response / behaviour of the client.

2. DISCUSSION

In this paper, current author stressed on need for studying intricacies and taking forward a new branch within psychology to deal with such intricacies called Intricacy psychology. This notion is integrated with the deeper case history taking for the new intervention meditation of the current author (the new intervention meditation is outlined in a different paper).

The Intricate Case History taking intended to help in the new intervention meditation of the current author and therefore included related concepts in case history taking. Such an intricate case history taking can be done by only psychologists qualified to the core and well trained for this purpose.

In the new intervention meditation of the current author, an expert is enlightened with two sets of baseline data (see diagram 1) about the client before beginning the meditation training – one set before completing the case history and one after completion of case history taking and before entering into orientation stage (see Diagram 3).

Need for psychologists and well trained qualified (as against educated quackery) psychologists strongly stressed for new intervention meditation of the current author has been shared in general by researchers on psychotherapy. Elly Quinlan and Frank P. Deane (2021) have also pointed out that psychologists should undergo training in such a way that they have enhanced confidence, uncertainty tolerance and effective integration into training.

The qualification (strictly psychologists qualified to the core) and specialized training only for qualified psychologists to become experts / Guru of new intervention meditation of current author is having a bearing in the wellbeing of clients and society as well.

While the structural integration of clients determines symptomatic changes and dropout, therapists should be trained on techniques to deal with structural integration and degree of dependence to prevent dropout and effective therapy (Immel, N., Dagnino, P., and Hunger-Schoppe, C. 2021). It is a common sense that dropout clients contribute to mental health issues in the society collectively, that the qualified should not only bother about individual clients but society collectively and deliver the duty of promoting a healthy society.

This paper is intended only to explain the concepts involved in the new Intervention Meditation of the current author.

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